

EIC User Group Newsletter

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Prepared by

M. Radici (marco.radici@pv.infn.it)

J. Arrington (johna@anl.gov)

NEWS

- The **last EIC Users Group Meeting ([EICUGM 2020](#))**, originally scheduled in Miami on 3-7 August, was held **online on 15-17 July**. On the **[first day](#)** several talks of **update** were delivered about the general status of the EICUG, of the EIC project and machine design, as well as from the DOE and NFS US funding agencies, followed by presentations from **country/community representatives from Europe, India and Canada**. On the **[second day](#)**, the **IB general meeting** included discussions on the **[EoI process](#)**, the upcoming call for detector proposals anticipated in March 2021, and potential modifications to the EICUG Charter, followed by **brief presentations from interested groups/consortia** on their plans for the **EoI**. The **[rest of the time](#)** was dedicated to short reports from various **Yellow Report** Physics and Detector Working Groups, followed by a general discussion on detector simulation and complementarity.
- On July 23, 24 and 27, the **EIC Detector R&D meeting** was held online. Progresses of all current proposals, as well as 4 new proposals, were actively discussed. See the **[web page](#)** for more information.
- In the **[“Yellow Report” menu of the EICUG web page](#)**, one can find the **calendar** of the next **“Yellow Report” workshops**, that will both be held **online**:
 3. 16-18 September 2020, CUA - Washington D.C. (USA)
 4. 19-21 November 2020, UCB - Berkeley (USA)

NEWS from the CHARTER COMMITTEE

- The Charter Committee has circulated to the entire Users Group a [survey](#) on the EICUG organizational structure, on effectiveness of communications and meetings, on responsibility of membership, on voting procedures, etc.. The **deadline** for filling the above form is next **Aug. 31st**. A pdf version of the form is available also [here](#).

NEWS from the ELECTION & NOMINATION COMMITTEE

- The elections for the office of **International Representative** on the EICUG Steering Committee have been closed. There were **two candidates**: Wouter Deconinck (Univ. Manitoba - Canada), Bedanga Mohanty (National Institute of Science and Education Research - NISER, India). **Wouter Deconinck** has been appointed the new position. Congratulations to him and many thanks to Bedanga Mohanty for running for these elections.

NEWS from the CONFERENCE & TALKS COMMITTEE

- Because of the Covid-19 lockdown, the **schedule** of next workshops and summer schools of interest for the EICUG has been **drastically modified**: many events have been **postponed** (sometimes with tentative dates), have **become on-line** meetings, or have been **cancelled** completely (see below). Thus, the speaking opportunities on behalf of the EICUG have been reduced. Nevertheless, there is **still the available opportunity** to give a talk (either on line or in person) at:
 1. [ICNFP 2020](#), Crete (Greece), 4-11 September 2020

- In any case, for consulting the list of **open EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/open> . For a list of **previous EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (often including also a link to the presentation). If you wish to recommend a candidate, including yourself, or if in general you wish to suggest new speakers (including yourself) to be considered for future invitations, please contact the Conference & Talks Committee at eicug-talks@eicug.org . Here, you can find also the general [talks guidelines](#) .

NEWS from the INSTITUTIONAL BOARD

- The **EICUG** currently stands at **1118 members**, from **238 institutions** in 31 countries. Theory members are approximately 25%, experimentalists 61%, experts in accelerators 13%, support 1%.

This is a pie chart illustrating how the 238 EICUG Institutions are split into the 6 world regions.

- Since last issue of the Newsletter, **seven more** institutions joined the EICUG:

- * Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul (Brazil)
- * Warsaw University of Technology (Poland)
- * University of Cincinnati (US)
- * South China Normal University (China)
- * Columbia University (US)
- * University of Puerto Rico (US)
- * University of Science and Technology of China (China)
- * China Institute of Atomic Energy (China)
- * Tsinghua University (China)
- * DAV College (India)

RECENT WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

See also <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (includes also links to some presentations)

Those events labeled by were held with on-line only format.

[Hard Probes](#), Austin (TX - USA), 31 May - 5 June 2020

[Workshop on Pion and Kaon Structure Functions at the EIC](#), CFNS-Stony Brook (NY-US), 2-5 June 2020

[Beam polarization and polarimetry at EIC](#), CFNS-Stony Brook (NY-US), 26 June, 29 June, 1 July, 2020

[Ad-hoc Meeting: Radiative Corrections](#), Stony Brook, 9-10 July 2020

[EIC Users Group Meeting 2020](#), Miami, 15-17 July 2020

[40th International Conference on High Energy Physics \(ICHEP 2020\)](#), Prague (Czech Republic), 28 July - 6 August 2020

[Photonuclear Gordon Conference](#), Holderness (NH - USA), 9-14 August 2020 **Cancelled**

[Hadron Collider Physics Summer School](#), Fermilab-CERN, 10-21 August 2020

UPCOMING WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

See also <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/upcoming> and <http://cnr2.kent.edu/~manley/BRAGmeetings.html> (the latter is temporarily not updated due to the current “stay at home” order)

The events labeled by will be held only on-line. If joined by “?”, it means that a decision is not yet taken.

[Origin of the Visible Universe: Unraveling the Proton Mass \(INT-20-77W\)](#), INT Seattle (WA - US), 4 - 8 May 2020 **Postponed**

[Transversity 2020](#), Pavia (Italy), 25-29 May 2020
Postponed to May 2021

[Tomography of light nuclei at an EIC](#), ECT*-Trento (Italy), 15-19 June 2020 **Postponed** to 25-29 October 2021

[LXX International Conference NUCLEUS-2020](#), Saint Petersburg (Russia), 26-30 June 2020 **Postponed** to 11-17 October 2020 ?

[Light-Cone 2020 \(LC2020\)](#), Jeju (Korea), 29 June - 4 July 2020
Postponed to 5-10 July 2021 as **LC2021**

[9th International Conference on New Frontiers in Physics \(ICNFP 2020\)](#), Kolymbari (Crete - Greece), 4 - 12 September 2020

[22nd International Conference on Particles and Nuclei \(PANIC2020\)](#), Lisbon (Portugal), 31 August - 4 September 2020
Postponed to 30 August - 3 September 2021

[24th International Spin Symposium SPIN2020](#), Matsue (Japan), 20-25 September 2020 **Postponed** to fall 2021

[Baryon 2020](#), Sevilla (Spain), 22-25 September 2020
Postponed to 19-22 October 2021 as **Baryon 2021**

[Silicon pixel-based particle vertex and tracking detectors towards the US Electron-Ion Collider Workshop](#), 2-4 September 2020

[Online Joint GlueX-EIC-PANDA Machine Learning Workshop](#), 21-25 September 2020

[New Physics Phenomena - Hadronic Contributions to New Physics Searches](#), Crete (Greece), 24-30 September 2020 **Postponed** Spring 2021

[5th International Conference on Particle Physics and Astrophysics \(ICCPA 2020\)](#), Moscow (Russia), 5-9 October 2020

[APS DNP Fall meeting](#), 29 October - 1 November 2020

[The 17th International Workshop on Hadron Structure and Spectroscopy \(IWHSS 2020\)](#), Trieste (Italy), 16-20 November 2020 ?

[Fast Machine Learning for Science Workshop](#), Southern Methodist Univ. (US), 30 November - 3 December 2020

[8th International Conference on High Energy Physics in the LHC era](#), Valparaiso (Chile), 4-8 January 2021

[QCD Evolution 2021 Workshop](#), UCLA (US), 10-14 May 2021

[The XIVth Quark Confinement and the Hadron Spectrum Conference](#), Stavanger (Norway), 2-7 August 2021

[Lepton-Photon 2021](#), Manchester (UK), 9-14 August 2021

Quarks and Nucleon Physics (QNP 2021), Bonn (Germany), 20-24 September 2021

[Workshop on the QCD Structure of the Nucleon \(QCD-N2021\)](#), Univ. Alcalà (Spain), 4-8 October 2021

UPCOMING SCHOOLS of INTEREST

[MCnet-CTEQ Summer School 2020](#), Bad Herrenalb (Germany), 2-12 August 2020 **Cancelled**

[International School for Strangeness Nuclear Physics](#)
(SNP2020), J-PARC, Tokai (Japan), 2-5 December 2020

